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TRENDS OF BROADBAND USAGE IN INDIA – AN OVERVIEW

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Abstract

Internet is playing a vital role in communication. Internet facility makes our communication easy and economy. In internet technology broadband is the recent development. India is one of the leading users of broadband in the world. The study has made an attempt to study the growth pattern of broadband usage in the world and in India. Internet is a milestone in communication technologies. Broadband is the internet technology which is used by most of the people in the world. The study found that during the 12 year period from 2001 to 2012, number of subscribers of broadband in India increased rapidly at a CAGR of 6 per cent. More than 150 Internet Service Providers (ISPs) are providing broadband services to customers. Among them BSNBL is playing as market leader. It contributes 59% of total broadband connections in the country. Eventhough huge number of people are using broadband, the penetration of Broadband usage in India seems to be very low. Hence there is a scope for ISPs to get more customers in terms of broadband connections.

Key words: internet, broadband, ISP, CAGR.

Introduction

Communication is essential for any living being. Even animals communicate with signals and sounds. From the time immemorial communication system was in practice for human beings. Over the period of time the different modes of communication was in practice. Initially servants of kings were used to communicate with kings of other countries. Latter well trained birds were used to send messages, then postal, telegram, telephone were used for communication. In the recent decades some modern technologies become popular such as mobile phone, internet and so on. Internet has been becoming popular for communication recently and people feel that it is easy mode of communication. Once dial-up technology was used, this was considered slow. Latter broadband technology was introduced. The term broadband refers to the wide bandwidth characteristics of a transmission medium and its ability to transport multiple signals and traffic types simultaneously. The growth of usage of broadband usage is becoming popular than any other mode of communication mode because of its speed and economy. India is the second largest country in terms of population and one of the fastest developing countries in terms of economy. Hence broadband usage in India is rapid. The study has made an attempt to know the growth pattern of broadband usage in India.

Literature Review

The Hindu (2014)^[1] reported that the mobile broadband subscriber base in India could grow to 600 million by 2020 from around 100 million now with 20 per cent of them using 4G. Business Standard (2014)^[2] reported that according to the recent Avendus Report, India has more than 160 million active internet users, of which 86 million access internet using their mobile devices. This also means that 46 per cent of the country relies on accessing the internet through broadband connections either from their home or office.

Statement of the Problem

Internet is playing a vital role in communication. Fewer decades ago only developed countries were using internet facility more, but now people of all the countries in the world are using internet facility. Internet facility makes our communication easy and economy. In internet technology broadband is the recent development. India is one of the leading users of broadband in the world. Hence it is necessary to study the growth pattern of broadband usage in the world and in India. Generally customers choose internet services providers by considering certain factors.

Objective of the Study

The study has been undertaken with the objective to study the growth pattern of broadband usage in India.

Methodology

The study has been made with secondary data. Secondary data were collected from various reports and internet sources for the period of 12 years from 2001 to 2012. The study used percentage analysis and compounded annual growth rate (CAGR) as statistical tools.

Results and Discussion : Trend of Internet Usage in India

India is one of the top countries in the world in internet usage, it is essential to know the growth pattern of internet users in India. Broadband technology of internet connection is the technology preferred by the people because of its speed and economy than earlier technologies. Broadband connection is available both wire and wireless connection. After the introduction of broadband internet connection, people started to get broadband connection. Table 1 provides the particulars of number of wired broadband subscribers in India for the period of 12 years from 2001 to 2012. It also gives the results of change over previous year and percentage of change over previous year on number of broadband connections in India.

Table 1: Trend of broadband connections in India

Year	No. of subscribers	Change over previous year	Percentage of change over Previous Year
2001	50,000	-	-
2002	82,409	32,409	64.82
2003	1,40,362	57,953	70.32
2004	2,35,000	94,638	67.42
2005	13,48,000	11,13,000	473.62
2006	23,00,000	9,52,000	70.62
2007	31,30,000	8,30,000	36.09
2008	52,80,000	21,50,000	68.69
2009	77,45,710	24,65,710	46.70
2010	1,09,90,000	32,44,290	41.88
2011	1,33,50,000	23,60,000	21.47
2012	1,43,06,000	9,56,000	7.16
CAGR	60.22		

Source: World Bank Statistics Report

Table 1 indicates that in 2001 there were 50,000 broadband connections in India it increased to 1,43,06,000 connections in 2012. It showed that number of broadband connections increased 286 times over 12 years period. Compound annual growth rate of broadband connections was 60.22 per cent. It was considered high and therefore there was rapid growth in number of broadband subscribers in India over the period. During 2002 broadband subscribers increased by 32,409 with 64.82 per cent growth rate over the previous year. During 2003 it increased to 70.32 per cent with 57,953 additional broadband subscribers. But during 2004 there was slight decline in percentage of change over previous year with 67.42 per cent with an additional subscribers of 94,638. During the year 2005 there was tremendous increase in broadband connections with an additional subscribers of 11,13,000 with 473.62 per cent growth over the previous year. During 2006 there was an additional subscribers of 9,52,000 with the growth rate of 70.62 per cent over the previous year. In the year 2007 the growth rate was very low at 36.09 per cent, but during the immediate next year the growth rate went up to 68.69 per cent over the previous year with an additional broadband connections of 21,50,000. From the year 2008 onwards eventhough the number of broadband connections were increasing the growth rate over the previous year was decreasing. The growth rate for 2009 stood at 46.7 per cent and it went down further to 41.88 per cent during 2010. During 2011 there was an additional broadband connections of 23,60,000, but growth rate went down to 21.47 per cent compared to 2010 (41.88 per cent). During 2012 the growth rate of broadband internet connections went down to 7.16 per cent and there was an additional connections of 9,56,000. The growth rate during 2012 was the lowest during the period of 12 years from 2001 to 2012. It was evidenced that the growth rate of broadband connections in India was rapid during the period. There were 1.43 crore connections during 2012 with 13.70 crore users.

Market Share of Various Internet Service Providers (ISPs)

According to TRAI, as on 31st March, 2012 there were 155 internet service providers who were providing broadband services in the country. Among them top 10 internet service providers, number of connections they had and their market share are presented in Table 2. Number of subscribers includes wire connections and wireless connections. But Table 1 provided the data related to wire connections of broadband in India.

Table 2: Internet Subscriber Base & Market Share of Top 10 ISPs

S.No	Internet Service Providers	Subscribers	Market Share (%)
1	Bharat Sanchar Nigam Ltd.	1,19,54,042	56.94
2	Reliance Communications Infrastructure Limited	26,80,107	12.77
3	Mahanagar Telephone Nigam Ltd.	24,77,200	11.80
4	Bharti Airtel Ltd.	14,12,317	6.73
5	Hathway Cable & Datacom Pvt. Ltd.	3,60,950	1.72
6	You Broadband & Cable India Pvt. Ltd.	3,01,513	1.44
7	Tikona Digital Networks Pvt Ltd	2,37,055	1.13
8	Beam Telecom Pvt. Ltd.	1,58,184	0.75
9	Tata Communications Internet Services Limited	1,57,862	0.75
10	Asianet Satellite Communications Ltd.	1,14,200	0.54
	Total of Top 10 ISPs	1,98,53,430	94.57
	Others	11,38,974	5.43
	Grand Total	2,09,92,404	100.00%

Source: FICCI-KPMG Report 2012

Table 2 shows that there were 21 million broadband subscribers in India during 2012. Among these connections the top ten companies held 19.85 million connections with the market

share of 94.57 per cent. It revealed that the top ten companies occupied more than 90 per cent of the market share and the rest of the companies held 5.43 per cent market share of broadband connections. Among the top ten companies which provide broadband internet services in the country, Bharat Sanchar Nigam Limited (BSNL) stood as market leader with 12 million broadband connections during the year 2012. The market share of BSNL in broadband internet services was 56.94 per cent. It occupied more than 50 per cent of the market share. It was also known that from the inception of broadband internet services, BSNL stood as market leader among the internet service providers (ISPs). Next to BSNL Reliance communication infrastructure limited occupied second place in market share of broadband internet services with the market share of 12.77 per cent. They held 2.7 million connections during 2012 though out the country. Mahanagar Telephone Nigam Limited (MTNL) stood third position in market share of providing broadband services in India with the market share of 11.80 per cent and they held 2.48 million connections. Bharti Airtel Limited occupied fourth place in market share with 6.73 per cent. Hathway Cable & Data Communication Private Limited, You Broadband & Cable India Private Limited and Timona Digital Network Private Limited occupied 5th, 6th and 7th places respectively with the market share of 1.72 per cent, 1.44 per cent and 1.13 per cent respectively. Other top 3 internet service provides had market share of less than 1 per cent. Beam Telecom Private Limited and Tata Communications Internet Services Limited had an market share at 0.75 per cent each and stood 8th and 9th positions respectively. Asianet Satellite Communications Limited occupied tenth position in market share with 0.54 per cent. Other than these top ten internet service providers all other internet service providers had 1.41 million broadband connections with the market share of 5.43 per cent.

Circle-wise Broadband Connections by BSNL

The results of table 2 showed that BSNL is the market leader in providing both wire and wireless broadband internet services in India. Among them wire connections of broadband is higher than wireless connections. Table 3 gives the data distribution of number of broadband connections provided by BSNL in 26 BSNL circles throughout the country, the percentage of each circle on total connections and their respective rank.

Table 3 below shows that BSNL has 26 circle offices throughout the country. Some circles providing services to a particular state and some circles providing services to more than one state. But in the states of Tamilnadu and Westbengal BSNL provides telecommunications services by two circles each. In Tamilnadu there is Tamilnadu circle and Chennai circle and in Westbengal there is Westbengal circle and Kolkata circle.

According to the table Karnataka circle of BSNL stood first having number of ADSL broadband connections with 10,36,483 connections and which occupied 11.22 per cent of the total broadband connections of BSNL followed by Andhrapradesh circle with 9,56,656 connections which accounted 10.35 per cent on the total connections of BSNL. Maharastra and Kerala stood at 3rd and 4th places respectively in terms of number of broadband connections with 8,84,772 and 8,79,415 connections. These circles contributed 9.58 per cent and 9.52 per cent of the total broadband connections of the total. Tamilnadu circle of BSNL stood at 5th place with 8,10,443 connections and it contributed 8.77 per cent of the total number of connections followed by Chennai circle of BSNL with 6,13,369 connections and which accounted 6.64 per cent of the total BSNL broadband connections of the country.

The table also showed that Andaman Nicobar Circle of BSNL had least number of broadband internet connections among the circles with only 6264 connections and which accounted only 0.07 per cent of the total BSNL broadband connections followed by North East – II circle with 18,617 connections (0.20 per cent of the total connections), North East – I circle with 35,022 connections (0.38 per cent of total), Jammu and Kashmir circle with 67,789 connections (0.73 per cent), Himachal Pradesh with 82,483 connections (0.89 per cent of total), Utranchal circle with 88,120 connections (0.95 per cent of total) and Chattisgarh circle with 91,647 connections and which accounted 0.99 per cent of the total connections.

Table 3: Circle wise ADSL BSNL Broadband connections (as on 30.6.2012)

Sl. No.	Circles	No. of connections	Percentage on total	Rank
1	Andaman & Nicobar	6,264	0.07	26
2	Andhra Pradesh	9,56,656	10.35	2
3	Assam	87,512	0.95	21
4	Bihar	99,808	1.08	17
5	Chhattisgarh	91,647	0.99	19
6	Chennai	6,13,369	6.64	6
7	Gujarat	6,05,239	6.55	7
8	Haryana	2,81,240	3.04	13
9	Himachal Pradesh	82,483	0.89	22
10	Jammu & Kashmir	67,789	0.73	23
11	Jharkhand	94,652	1.02	18
12	Karnataka	10,36,483	11.22	1
13	Kerala	8,79,415	9.52	4
14	Kolkata	3,56,276	3.86	10
15	Madhya Pradesh	3,08,736	3.34	12
16	Maharashtra	8,84,772	9.58	3
17	North East-I	35,022	0.38	24
18	North East-II	18,617	0.20	25
19	Orissa	1,79,111	1.94	15
20	Punjab	5,27,710	5.71	8
21	Rajasthan	4,20,915	4.56	9
22	Tamil Nadu	8,10,443	8.77	5
23	Uttar Pradesh East	3,30,218	3.57	11
24	Uttar Pradesh West	2,25,639	2.44	14
25	Uttaranchal	88,120	0.95	20
26	West Bengal	1,51,930	1.64	16

Source: TRAI

According to circle wise data Karnataka circle stood first in holding number of broadband connections and Tamilnadu occupied fifth place followed by Chennai circle. When state wise data was considered the state of Tamilnadu was provided broadband internet services of BSNL by two circles such as Tamilnadu and Chennai circle. Total number of connections held by these two circles together accounted 14,23,812 connections and which contributed 15.41 per cent of the total number of BSNL broadband connections in the country. But the state of Karnataka contributed only 11.22 per cent of the total connections in the country. In terms of state wise data Tamilnadu stood first in having number of BSNL broadband connections as on 30.6.2012. Another state which was provided BSNL broadband services by two circles which was Westbengal, it had two circles called Westbengal and Kolkata. Total number of connections of these two circles together stood at 5,08,205 connections and it accounted 5.50 per cent of the total number of connections in the country, so it was evidenced from the table that Tamilnadu was the top state which held highest number of BSNL broadband connections in the India.

Conclusion

Internet is a milestone in communication technologies. Broadband is the internet technology which is used by most of the people in the world. India is one of the fastest developing countries in the world and usage of broadband also is increasing at a higher rate. During the 12 year period from 2001 to 2012, number of subscribers of broadband in India increased rapidly at a CAGR of 6 per cent. More than 150 ISPs are providing broadband services to customers. Among them BSNL is playing as market leader. It contributes 59% of total broadband connections in the country. Eventhough huge number of people are using broadband, the penetration of Broadband usage in India seems to be very low. Hence there is a scope for ISPs to get more customers in terms of broadband connections.

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